

Fourth year internship report
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« THE ROBOTIC THERAPY: THE ASSESSMENT OF AN ACTIVE ORTHOSIS FOR THE REHABILITATION OF FLEXION AND EXTENSION OF THE WRIST FOR PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS »

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INTRODUCTION : PROBLEM AND WORK OBJECTIVES

I. PARKINSON'S DISEASE

The Parkinson disease is a neurodegenerative disease that affects the central nervous system. It is a progressive, chronic movement disorder that affects the control of muscle and balance. Parkinson [1] is a progressive disease because it progresses with time, and it is a neurodegenerative disease because during the disease there is a loss of neurons in the brain. There is a loss of particular kind of neuron: the dopamine neurons. These neurons make a little chemical signal called dopamine and allowed us to make normal movement. This dopamine neurons live in the substantia nigra, an area of the brain. When the dopamine neurons are lost, there is a reduction in the amount of dopamine in the brain and we can start to see the main movement signs of Parkinson's disease. The dopamine neurons are used to make a lot of our dopamine and in the Parkinson's disease case there are not in the substantia nigra situated in the midbrain yet. And when there is a reduction in dopamine, the main symptom of Parkinson's disease start.

Figure 1: Schema of Synaptic junction

Figure 2: Parkinson's disease degeneracies beginning

Without dopamine, the synapse doesn't work and the main signs of Parkinson's disease start to appear.

The first sign is the shakiness, which can be a form of tremor focus in the hand and the fingers. There are two types of tremor: the resting tremor and the action tremor. The resting tremor is the most common in Parkinson's disease. We can see the combination of both of them in a patient. The character of the tremor can change during the illness.

The second sign is the stiffness, or we can say rigidity. It is felt when the patient bends part of their body. This sign concerns the arm, the wrist or the leg. When this sign appears, the movement of the body becomes not smooth, not fluid anymore it feels really rigid like there is a resistance in the body motion.

A third main sign is the bradykinesia. It is a kind of slowed-down movements. This symptom takes the patient longer to complete a movement. It concerns the muscle of the body, we can see a slowness of voluntary movement. The particularity of this sign is that the patient can do the movement, is just that it takes a lot longer for them to do it.

We can talk about the problems with balance for the fourth sign of Parkinson's disease. The patient feels unsteady or really unstable when he walks around or stands. This postural instability occurred in the third stage of Parkinson's disease, it is a later consequence.

Furthermore, all the patient with the Parkinson's disease have all of these signs. The combination of the symptom depends of the sexes, age, stage of the patient. The causes of Parkinson's disease are not known for most of the case, these cases are called idiopathic cases. It is mean that the cause is unknown yet.

Therapy:

There are different ways for dumping the Parkinson's disease symptoms. We can put forward three groups of treatment:

- Drugs
- Surgery
- Rehabilitation

First of all, the obvious treatment of Parkinson's disease must involve medication: the way of many medications work is by replacing dopamine in the brain or increasing it inside because the cell producer of dopamine has degenerated during the disease. We can note some common drugs for this treatment: dopaminergic, anticholinergic, anticholinergic, anticholinergic.

When patients have this disease for several years, the medication doesn't work anymore. The next step of treatment is the surgery.

The aim of the surgery is to disable areas in the brain that are causing the problems of movement, like the tremor. But the Parkinson's disease is a progressive disease, it means that it will continue to develop with time. The most common kind of surgery is the pallidotomy, or the deep brain stimulation (DBS). This procedure consists by implanting electrical stimulators in the midbrain. The results are excellent for some years.

The medication therapy and surgery therapy cannot stop the disease, these methods can just be helpful for managing the symptoms and making the patient has a better quality of life for as long as possible.

Then, in the aim to increase the movement habilitation of the patient, there are some methods to help the patient to gain physical abilities. We can note the physical therapy, the speech therapy nor the robotic therapy. This last method is a safe way to help patient with Parkinson's disease and it allows an intensive rehabilitation. The robotic therapy is used for individuals with light or severe motor deficits.

II. THE PROJECT

When I contacted the Professor Adriano O. Andrade for the first time by email, he proposed me to work with his team in a robotic therapy project. His project related to the assessment and control of an active orthotic device that can be used for the rehabilitation of the wrist by the Parkinson disease patient.

The aim of the work is to explore the ergonomic effect of an active orthosis used in rehabilitation of flexion and extension of the wrist in the Parkinson's disease patient cases.

In this way, the orthosis is imagined to be a training device which can help the patients to regain amplitude in the movement of their wrist. The movement that is targeted in this work is the motion of flexion and extension. Moreover, this device should help the parkinsonians to reduce the tremor of the hand.

Figure 3: Schema of the active orthosis

III. MY ROLE

For the understanding of the purpose of the project, I was missioned to go regularly at the Parkinson's disease association the Friday afternoon to learn more about how the Parkinson symptom look like in real life. I saw by myself the main symptoms of the disease. My supervisor expected to me that I collect data about the amplitude of the movement of the wrist for each patient. I had to analyzed these parameters for each class of patient:

- The amplitude of the wrist flexion (angle in degree)
- The amplitude of the wrist extension (angle in degree)

Then, when I arrived at the laboratory for the first time, I met my work team and my supervisor introduced what he expected of me about the project.

He explained that I have to find a way to make the device works by creating a firmware in the way to enabled the actuator of the prototype. So, I was supposed to make move the prosthesis in two directions: the flexion and the extension of the wrist. This was the main part of my work.

For make this part works, I have to use the software Visual Studio to create a code for the controller. The main component of the device is a linear servomotor which is connected to the controller.

Moreover, this project focus on two mains symptoms: the rigidity of the muscle and the hand tremor.

In the way to moving forward, I have to work in two different firmware: one for reduce the tremor and another to helping the movement of flexion and extension of the wrist for the Parkinson's disease patients. The final purpose of my work is to program the actuator to provide a mechanical assistance in the wrist's motion by the patients.

Figure 4: Picture of the orthosis fit in the forearm

THE LABORATORY

I. THE LOCATION

Firstly, I have chosen to make my internship abroad to improve my English language and discover another way to be an engineer. Then, I am very attracted by the robotic therapy and especially the prosthesis area, so I had make some research about it in different laboratory. The NIATS [2] offer a large choice of project and scientific research. The Adriano O. Andrade's project inspired me to go to Brazil and join the team of the laboratory.

So, I did my internship in Brazil in the city of Uberlandia where I stayed sixteen weeks. Uberlandia is located in the north of the state of Minas Gerais and has 600 000 inhabitants.

During my internship, I was part of the UFU like a student and I worked especially at the Center for Innovation and Technology Assessment in Health (NIATS).

This university is a public institution and has 21 000 students divided in three campuses. Most of students are in engineering class but UFU offers various courses: architecture, medicine, physical education, literature, art and physics.

Figure 5: institution and localization of the NIATS

II. THE NIATS

The Center for Innovation and Technology Assessment in Health (NIATS) is a research group of the Federal University of Uberlandia (UFU) registered with the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) and recognized by the Ministry of Health (Department of Science and Technology, DECIT).

The mission of NIATS is to investigate, develop, evaluate and compare technologies in healthcare that can be used in clinical practice in order to meet the demands of the National Health System. The center tends to be an international reference in the evaluation and development of technologies in health.

This laboratory is situated in the Santa Monica campus of UFU, at the block 1A and it is managed by the Professor Adriano O. Andrade, this professor is also my supervisor during the internship.

Moreover, the center is composed of various profiles like engineers, researchers, undergraduate students, internship students. This combination of member represents a real great strength and the contribution of those different points of view for the same work permit the emergence of real problematics about the discussion about the results of the project.

Since 2012, the NIATS group is part of the Brazilian Network for Health Technology Assessment (REBRATS) and it is recognized nationally and worldwide for its technical, scientific, social and administrative actions.

Furthermore, the NIATS is composed by five main research areas:

- Health Technology Assessment, with the aim of evaluating and comparing the clinical and technical performance of new and existing electro-medical technologies
- Biomedical Signal Processing, which is focused on creating and using signal processing techniques aimed at modelling and analyzing biological systems
- Biomechanics, focused upon the development and use of systems for monitoring and evaluation of human movement
- Telemedicine, which is focused on the conception of systems and protocols that allow decision making as well as remote monitoring of biomedical information
- Medical Imaging, centered on imaging evaluation, control and quality, diagnostic imaging, and digital image processing

I am part of the biomechanics area for my internship.

III. MATERIALS

In the way to give the better work, I was part of the NIATS laboratory. I had one computer and I could use all the electronic tools that I had need to improve the prototype.

Moreover, I had to use the Faulhaber Motion Manager 6 software to program the linear DC motor.

I worked with one actuator in a support for make all my test and I had the prototype of the prosthesis at disposal to experiment if the movement is available or not by the patients.

To use the actuator, I needed a GBF of the laboratory.

Then, I used a goniometer to measure the different angles of flexion and extension when I gone to the Parkinson's Association.

I also used the user manual of the software and the actuator that I had to work with.

Figure 6: My work tools

Figure 7: The prototype of experimentation

Figure 8: GBF with a regular 12V of tense

Figure 9: Prosthesis

Figure 10: The goniometer

MISSION 1 : DATA COLLECTION

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease is the second main neurodegenerative disease in the world after the Alzheimer disease. This disease affects more than 6 million people worldwide and 160 000 cases in France.

The victims of this neurodegenerations increase every year and become a serious public health disease in the world. Men are more affected than women and the diagnostic start after sixty-year-old. Moreover, ten percent of patient are diagnosed before fifty-year-old.

The rigidity of the muscle described well the Parkinson's disease, 70 percent of the patient suffer of tremor and 78 percent of them suffer of bradykinesia.

PARKINSON'S DISEASE DISTRIBUTION

Figure 11: Distribution of PD among men and women in world

During the first month of my internship, I had to make a lot of research about the Parkinson's disease. In this way, I read a lot of publication, saw some video about the symptom, talked with specialist like physiotherapists about the disease and visited the PD association.

The main question we can forward is "What is the purpose of the prosthesis?".

The perspective of this work is to include the robotic therapy in the physical rehabilitation. The three main symptoms of Parkinson's disease are movements problem: bradykinesia, rigidity (increase in muscle tone) and tremor. We hope that this robotic device could improve the motion capacity of the patients. This prosthesis is made for attain an increase of the range motion of the wrist. So, we have to keep in mind that the prosthesis will be using in the aim to decrease the muscular rigidity. With this device, we cannot interpose for the bradykinesia or the tremor directly.

But if the rigidity decreases during the therapy, we can expect that consequently the patient will gain a certain amplitude of his wrist motion and logically he can

dump the tremor naturally and decreases the other symptoms. So, this prosthesis is only made for train the wrist of the patient to make flexion and extension for reduce the rigidity. If the rigidity decreases we can gain amplitude of the movement.

The second question is "How the patient can use this prosthesis?".

The purpose of the prosthesis is to organize training sessions with a physiotherapist. The patient fit the device in the wrist and the orthosis is programmed to help the patient for doing movement of flexion and extension. The prosthesis will move in two directions for following the wrist and increase the amplitude of the movement.

We can imagine that this repetition of movement for the simulation of the muscle could feel boring or unattractive for some patient, especially if it's a daily training. In this way, my supervisor proposed to Morgan LeDortz, a fourth-year student in the same school institution of me, to work in a serious game to motivate patients to do this training. The purpose of the game is to focus the patient for doing fluidly the repetition of the movement and to encourage them to practice the repetition. She programmed the serious game with Unity, we worked together for raise the idea of the game but the creation of the game is part of her internship topic, so I did not interpose in the programming of the game.

Figure 12: Schema showing the main mission of the work

So, we can easily understand that the purpose of the prosthesis is not to cure the disease itself but the idea is to improve the daily life.

Indeed, the wrist represent a direct access to the hand. And the hand allows people to do whatever they want: take object, eat, drink, speak, write, communicate and so and.

If this open way to life is broken, people would lose themselves in psychological degeneracies and lose any motivation to do anything. The idea is to keep this access work providing a mechanical assistance for the wrist motion.

Figure 13: Expectations after the training period using the prosthesis

This picture shows the purpose of the prosthesis, is not to cure the disease but to help patients to gain amplitude of the movement. The main objective is the wrist rehabilitation.

The first problem using this prosthesis is the rigidity of the limb. Patients could react differently and cannot use the prosthesis in the same way. For sure it will be easier to train the least affected patients. Conversely, for the most serious patients, time and motivation is necessary.

So, the question is how we can measure the rigidity for creating a data base. During the Monday's meeting, I shared with my supervisor and Luiza to find the better way to measure objectively the rigidity. The first idea was to use a goniometer.

My first mission coming with the measurement of the rigidity.

II. THE PARKINSON'S DISEASE ASSOCIATION

The Parkinson's disease association is an association which gathered some Parkinson specialist, nurses, physiotherapists and volunteers who welcome each week three groups of patient to train them to move their body. I gone regularly in this place to see how the Parkinson's disease symptoms looks like in real life.

My first objective to visiting the association is to measure the amplitude of the flexion and extension of the wrist.

III. MY ROLE

During the first month of my internship, I used to go at the association each Friday. When I went to the Parkinson's disease Association, I had to observe how the main symptoms take part of the body.

Problematic:

The first difficulty was how I can quantify the rigidity of the wrist. With the simple means that we had to be able to quantify this rigidity, we chose to measure the angle of flexion and extension of the wrist.

So, for that had to know how I can measure the rigidity of the wrist. During the Monday's meeting, in September, I talked with my supervisor and a physiotherapist, Luiza, and we propose to use a goniometer to measure this amplitude.

Consequently, my mission in the association was to collect some data about symptom. I had to measure the amplitude of the flexion and extension of the wrist. We focused about the wrist because the prosthesis is fit for this part of the body.

IV. DATA PROCESSING

For measuring the rigidity of the wrist, I went to the association with Morgan LeDortz. First, we used the goniometer to calculate the angle between the forearm and the flexion of the hand. We repeated the same calculation with the extension of the hand. We made a list of patient with different criterions: sex, age, stage of disease and we picked up the different values.

Due to the precision error, we suggested finding another way to measure this angle. We decided to use the Piximètre software.

Piximètre is a metrology software. We had to download it and we could use it to measure the object.

The patients are separated by different stages of disease.

There are three stages:

- Stage I: Beginning of disease
- Stage II: Intermediate disease
- Stage III: Serous patient

Thus, during the sessions at the association, we took pictures of flexion and extension of the wrist and we measured the angle with the software. Then we compared the different results.

Figure 14: Screens of pictures taken for Piximetre measurements

V. RESULTS

Values with the goniometer:

Sex	Age	Stage (I,II ,III)	Angle flexion	Angle extension
♂	60	I	Right hand: 133 Left hand: 132	Right hand: 133 Left hand: 109
♂	63	I	R: 120 L: 140	R:102 L: 120
♂	64	II	R: 120 L: 120	R:120 L:120
♂	78	II	R:122 L:122	R:110 L:110
♂	71	II	R:120 L:128	R:120 L:112
♀	61	I	R:123 L:122	R:108 L:116
♀	71	I	R:120 L:121	R:140 L:120
♀	55	I	R:125 L:123	R:111 L:112
♀	59	II	R:123 L:135	R:110 L:123
♀	67	II	R:121 L:132	R:116 L:110
♀	76	II	R: 124 L:120	R:116 L:135

Figure 15:Table of values taken with the goniometer

Value with Piximètre software:

Sex	Age	Stage (I,II ,III)	Angle flexion	Angle extension
♂	60	I	Right hand: 123 Left hand: 132	Right hand: 132 Left hand: 122
♂	63	I	R: 121 L: 147	R:105 L: 122
♂	64	II	R: 124 L: 118	R:110 L:120
♂	78	II	R:120 L:120	R:111 L:110
♂	71	II	R:122 L:127	R:125 L:115
♀	61	I	R:122 L:120	R:118 L:113
♀	71	I	R:129 L:125	R:111 L:122

♀	55	I	R:124 L:122	R:112 L:112
♀	59	II	R:127 L:135	R:110 L:123
♀	67	II	R:120 L:132	R:116 L:110
♀	76	II	R: 124 L:122	R:115 L:136

Figure 16: Table of values taken with the Piximetre software

Red: error > 10 degree

Yellow: 5>error >10

Green: 5>error

CONCLUSION

The problematic is still relevant because it is not easy to correctly measure this rigidity precisely with a tool with which we have a lot of uncertainty. So, I think that this tool is not adapted if we want to measure objectively the rigidity in Parkinson's disease.

Moreover, we reject these values because there is a big difference in measurement with these two techniques.

The results are not very interpretable because only 27% of the values are consistent with the measurement techniques, so it is not reliable.

Consequently, I will not include these values to set the prosthesis.

MISSION 2 : THE STABILITY OF THE ELECTRICAL PART OF THE DEVICE

I. INTRODUCTION

During the experimentation with the prototype, my supervisor and I noticed that there was something wrong with the electrical connection of the device. So, we made different test of encoder to find the problem and we finally concluded that some electrical cables could be broken inside. The prototype was unstable. My secondary mission come here: I had to fix up the electrical part of the prototype.

I will start to describe this mission before my part about the code of my report in the aim to make a logic development of my work during my internship although my first mission was to drive the actuator of the prototype.

II. PRESENTATION OF THE ACTIVE ORTHESIS

The orthesis is a wrist prosthesis designed to be worn on the forearm and equipped with an actuator of type linear DC servomotor by the Faulhaber company, the reference of this actuator is LM2070-080-11 [3] . This component is the main part of the device: the control and the motion of it allows to reach the objective of the work. First, I will present the entire prosthesis and later I will explain more about the actuator.

The orthesis is composed by different pieces. Like I already said, there is an actuator which represent the principal part of the device. This actuator presents a central axis and two lateral axes. This part of the prosthesis can be programmed to actuate the sliding of the central axis.

Figure 17: Presentation of the device with the different axes

We can distinguish two main structures of the device:

- the hand structure
- the forearm structure

Moreover, there is a 3D forearm support designed and printed to safety stabilize put behind the forearm.

Figure 17: The Linear Servomotor

Figure 18: The controller

The control of the linear motor allows the patient to realize physical exercises for the wrist rehabilitation, especially the flexion and extension.

In this way, I had to work about two symptoms of the Parkinson's disease: the rigidity and the tremor.

III. IMPROVING THE DEVICE : THE ELECTRONIC CONNECTIONS OF THE PROTOTYPE

For that, Professor Adriano put me in touch with the Professor Sergio: I worked with him for two weeks to find the good way to make the connections works again. First, we tried to resold these wires but those were very fragile and it didn't work.

We fixed up each cable of who link the controller with the driver. In total, we realized 8 solders:

- Motor C
- Motor B
- Motor A
- Ground
- Ucc
- Sensor C
- Sensor B
- Sensor A

Figure 19: Different step of the work

IV. RESULTS

After this, we send some simple command to evaluate the reliability of the connection.

All the connection worked well.

V. CONCLUSION

The prototype was not reliable when I arrived in the laboratory. The failure of my first tests with my code drive us to find the electrical problem of the prototype. The material is ready to be managed by the programming part.

MISSION 3 : ENCODE THE CONTROLLER

I. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the device is to allow a mechanical assistance to patients who are not able to perform flexions and extensions by themselves. In this way, my role was to make move the actuator in two directions to help these movements using a firmware that I can send to the controller of the servomotor. In this part of my report, I will explain how I build a path of commands using the software to control the actuator.

In the aim to start the development of the code, I needed:

- an actuator
- a controller
- a driver

II. USING OF FAULHABER MOTION MANAGER 6

At the beginning of my work, I started to read the data sheet of the device for each component. Before that, I was supposed to use Visual Studio to write a script for control the actuator. But researching in the bibliography of the component, I noticed that there is another software that I could use for creating my firmware: Faulhaber Motion Manager 6. Then I had proposed to my supervisor to use this tool in my work, he agreed and gave me all the using protocols documents about this software.

Faulhaber Motion Manager 6 can be used to access settings and parameters of the connected control. We can create sequence programs to be executed on the device. I have to use it for configuring the drive system with the motion and other parameters (speed, velocity, strength). The software is used to make the communication between the software interface and the device controller, then we can operate some command of control to move the actuator.

Figure 20: User interface of the software

The software allows us to access settings and parameters of the connected control. We can create sequence programs and create some command to be edited, transferred and executed on the device.

I can program a sequence with this software using the visual basic script (VB Script).

The user interface of the software present different windows for the various tasks. We can access to the header menu, the toolbar, the footer, docking area, node explorer, editor and the terminal to encode.

Protocol:

First, I have to establish the connection between the controller and the software, I make the initial startup using the COM interface with the serial port COM3.

Then I choose the motion controller and I connected with the device MCLM3006S-RS. The connection between the controller and the device is enable.

So, I opened a new project with the button "new project" in the user interface. I can use the different commands of the toolbar to create motion with the actuator. I will explain more about the code in the next part. I can use also the terminal to input commands manually and see directly if there is an error or status message.

The device used in the project is part of the MC V2.X family: the specified commands can be send directly as ASCII characters or as a CAN telegram via the Faulhaber software channel. For my part, I used only the CAN telegram because I didn't have the time to test the ASCII way. But I learn with Professor Sergio how it works and how I can use it. We planned to try to send command with this way but because of our different schedule we could not test it.

III. DEVELOPEMENT OF THE FIRMWARE

According to the value I had to use, I made a sequence of command that allow the actuator to move in the right then the left direction.

After this, I include this code in an endless loop to repeat the sequence. The loop was the better way to develop the training sequence.

Thus, I changed the parameters of the strength and the velocity to adapt the game for Parkinson's disease patient. for that, I interpose in the acceleration and deceleration command changing the value.

I obtain this following code for the creation of motion.

Figure 21: Code used for the motion of the device

IV. DUMPING THE TREMOR

During my several tests with my codes, I found a command who permit the prosthesis to go back to the initial position. If I include this command in a loop, I can obtain a way to manage the tremor of the hand. Indeed, the strength of the motion given by the device and the return home position is useful for dump the tremor of the limb. But of course, this effect is only reliable if the patient wears the prosthesis. Is not a therapy but a technical assistance.

```

16      ;Endless loop
17 A1
18      ;do something
19      LA4000
20      M
21      DELAY10
22      LA-4000
23      M
24      DELAY10
25 JMP1

```

Figure 22: Endless loop. The home position (HO) command is not written in the code but it permits the return position of the device

V. HELP THE WRIST MOTION : FLEXION AND EXTENSION

Figure 23: Result of the programming. My supervisor watches his hand moving thank to the prosthesis without effort

I tested the device with my own wrist. The device is linked to the controller and I run the program: I can follow the movement of the orthosis easily. The movement is repeated because of the loop that I created.

VI. RESULTS

The actuator response is good estimated. The expectation for the first code is satisfied: the device can help the movement of flexion and extension of the wrist.

We can imagine using it for health volunteers for evaluate the acceptance of the device.

On the other hand, I think that we can work more to manage the different parameter: velocity and strength.

I focus myself for creating a reliable code but I had not enough time to improve the representative commands.

CONCLUSION

After different test of code, I retain two of them for present the project. The first is reliable to move the wrist on flexion and extension.

The second permits to manage the tremor when the patient is wearing the device.

THE 26TH CBEB

I. INTRODUCTION

The Brazilian Society of Biomedical Engineering (SBEB) is a group which represent the civil institution of scientific character and acting throughout the national territory of Brazil , with the purpose of bringing together the biomedical engineering careers.

The SBEB was founded on December 18, 1975 and gathered approximately 400 associates in the areas of Bioengineering, Medical Engineering, Clinical Engineering and Rehabilitation Engineering.

Since its inception, it has been conducting congresses, symposia and meetings, publishing scientific publications and working with government and class organs. Moreover, SBEB has contributed to the scientific advance, exchange of experiences and definitions of policies in the areas of health and technology, encouraging the formation and consolidation of teaching programs and research groups, as well as promoting the dissemination and recognition of Biomedical Engineering in the Brazilian country.

Every two years, the CBEB congress is promoted by the Brazilian Society of Biomedical Engineering.

It is organized by researchers linked to a national teaching or research institution and counts on the collaboration of the scientific community active in the Brazilian area of biomedical engineering .

This event use to bring gather academic communities, researchers, scientists from various fields, undergraduate and graduate students, as well as representatives from industry, commerce and governments, so that everyone can discuss and present their scientist paper and ideas on key problems of biomedical engineering.

Figure 24: CBEB congress with Edgar Lamounier, Ophelie Fourbet, Morgan LeDortz, me, Adriano Andrade, Antoine Augé

I went to this congress which took place in Búzios with my work team and Antoine Augé, Ophélie Fourbet and Morgan LeDortz. This event started on October 21 and lasted five days. In this part, I will present one conference that I retained.

II. THE CONGRESS

The title of the conference is "A serious game based on myo-armband for upper-limb rehabilitation exercises". I chose to present this topic because it is part of my project. Morgan LeDortz worked about this subject.

This game is an assistive technology and gathers different areas of study: rehabilitation, educational, engineering, biotechnology.

The goal is to expand functional skills, gain autonomy and independence, raise the quality of life and the social inclusion.

The serious game is designed to intentionally stimulate other characteristics rather than pure amusement, as its first objective. It can assist patients and health professionals, motivating the user to execute the exercise movements during the rehabilitation sessions, using a variety of devices, with goals and scores to be reached.

The purpose of the conference is to evaluate the SG for upper-limb rehabilitation based on the myo-armband with the goal of improving its usability before its usage with impaired patients.

Materials and methods:

The process of the serious game needs:

- Game engine – Unity
- 3D modeling software – Blender
- Game genre – Action (suitable for physical rehabilitation)

The developed SG is part of a Virtual-R System which is an SG platform. We need a Kinect 2, a Myo and a HTC Vive.

Description of the SG:

When the user executes the rehabilitation exercise, the gun shot a bullet and the number of remaining bullets is reduced by 1. If the player hits a target the score count adds 10 points.

Practical application:

Before the implementation of the designed SG with patients, it was tested by five health volunteers to verify its usability and acceptance. Each participant tried the SG with a free time, so they were able to adapt to it. The duration of the test was 3 sessions of 10 repetitions each. Then, the volunteers answered the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire and were asked to leave comments and recommendation about the SG.

Results:

The SUS results show that the system was well evaluated by the volunteers with a score above 70.

Users were able to use the myo-armband properly, as all the users reached a score over 60, which means they hit at least, 6 objects over 10.

Conclusion:

The development of a SG passes through a sequence of design, implementation, tests and modifications before reaching its final version.

The evaluation of the SG by users indicates a good acceptance and usability.

However, some changes must be made to improve user's usability.

As future works this SG will be tested again with a higher number of health users and health professionals before its usage with patients with tendon/nerve injuries or forearm/wrist fractures.

If I make a link with this subject and my internship topic, I can imagine that this game is totally adapted.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Symposium on Virtual and Augmented Reality (SVR) represent a conference on virtual reality and augmented reality in Brazil, sponsored annually by the Brazilian Computer Society (SBC). This year the congress took place on October 29 and lasted 4 days in Iguazu Foz.

This event brings together researchers, students and professionals from various academic, industrial and commercial areas interested in the advances in and applications of virtual reality and augmented reality.

The symposium aims to bring together participants, encouraging the exchange of experiences and facilitating interaction between research groups and creating better conditions for the development of new inter-institutional research groups.

Moreover, the SVR is composed of some activities that include:

- Pre-Symposium
- Short Courses
- Invited keynotes (national and international)
- Technical sessions for presentation of selected papers
- Workshops
- Exposition of products by companies operating in the virtual reality and augmented reality market

II. THE CONGRESS

During this congress, I attended most of the conference.

I was registered to participate in short courses.

I chose two sessions of course among the four proposed:

- V-REP robot simulator as a validation tool for computer vision
- VR and AR for business: a practical experience with ViroReact and JavaScript

I went to the V-REP session with Antoine and Morgan. The teacher challenged us to develop a virtual atmosphere game with V-REP. We were in competition with the other participants of the course.

At the end of the session, our team was selected and we won the contest. The SVR group offered us a drone and a virtual reality helmet.

CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

My internship was full of different missions. I spent most of time of my work to learn about Parkinson's disease, Faulhaber manager motion software, the prototype already launched and the Portuguese language I start my work in the Parkinson association and finally.

My main work consisted in developing a program for make move the prosthesis. But I also focused myself about the improvement of the electronical part because it is was not reliable when I arrived, and participating in congress and meeting.

I am particularly proud of this project because it is a exclusive project about the wrist rehabilitation in Parkinson's disease, I mean that no other research group worked on this project before, it's a novel idea of my supervisor. It the first robotic therapy focus in the rehabilitation of limb for this disease.

My work team bring me a lot of knowledge during my internship and I am satisfied to give them a positive result of my work.

Moreover, this project will be present for the 41st International Engineering in Medicine and Biology Conference (EMBC 2019) in Berlin the next July and I probably will be part of it thank to Professor Adriano Andrade.

However, this project has not results about experimentation with patient or volunteers yet, so we have not results about the acceptance of the prosthesis. The lack of these information does not permit us to confirm if the project is reliable or not for the rehabilitation and if it is adapted for Parkinson's disease patients. This project is still a research subject and the next expectations for the future are the test with health volunteers.

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ANNEXES

<i>Annex 1: Summary of the IFTM conference.....</i>	<i>36</i>
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Annex 1: Summary of the IFTM conference

During my internship, my supervisor invited me to present the project to the Federal Institution of Triangularly Mineiro. This institution is located in the campus of Uberlandia.

I went to this place on October 15 with my work team to give a little conference exhibiting my role in the project.

I made this poster for the presentation. It shows my different roles and expectations.

Robotic therapy: the wrist orthesis for the PD

OBJECTIF OF THE PROJECT

TOOLS

MISSIONS

- Encode with the software Faulhaber Motion Management 6
- Control the movement of the actuator:
 - Paramaters: velocity, speed, strength
 - 2 direction : flexion/extension

THE AIM

Dumping the tremor :

Find a returning position code

Helping the flexion and extension

Create a code to move in 2 direction the DC servomotor

Annex 2: Parameters used with Faulhaber Manager Motion

PARÂMETROS

- **LA** → 0.00 ($-1.8 \cdot 10^9$... $1.8 \cdot 10^9$);
- **LR** → 0.00 ($-2.14 \cdot 10^9$ e $2.14 \cdot 10^9$);
- **PP** → 10.00 (1 a 255);
- **PD** → 10.00 (1 a 255);
- **POR** → 127.00 (1 a 255);
- **I** → 50.00 (1 a 255);
- **SR** → 1.00 (1 a 20);
- **SP** → 10000.00 (0 a 30000.0 rpm);
- **LPC** → 2370.00 (0 a 12000.0 mA);
- **LCC** → 790.00 (0 a 12000.0 mA);
- **AC** → 10000.00 (0 a 30000.0 m/s^2);
- **DEC** → 30000.00 (0 a 30000.0 m/s^2).

COMANDO	FUNÇÃO
DI	Desabilitar drive
EM	Habilitar drive
M	Iniciar movimento
LA	Carregar a posição absoluta
LR	Carregar a posição relativa
PP	Carregar controle de posição proporcional
PD	Carregar controle de posição Diferencial
POR	Carregar velocidade proporcional

COMANDO	FUNÇÃO
I	Carregar controle de posição integral
SR	Carregar taxa de amostragem
SP	Carregar a velocidade máxima
LPC	Carregar corrente de pico
LCC	Carregar corrente contínua
AC	Carregar comando de aceleração
DEC	Carregar comando de desaceleração

Annex 3: Test scripts

The screenshot shows the FAULHABER Motion Manager software interface. The main editor window displays a test script with the following code:

```

29
30
31 *LA2000
32 *M
33 *V100
34 *LA-2000
35 *V100
36 *M
37 *DELAY100
38
39 ;Counter loop
40 *A2
41 ;do something
42
43 *LA4000
44 *SP1000
45 *M
46 *DELAY100
47 *DA,NZ2 ;decrement A and jump to A1 while A > 0
48 ;A=0: next statements
49

```

The terminal window shows the following communication log:

Time	Message
11:48:10.506	Interface COM3 closed
11:48:10.725	Interface COM3 open (9600 bit/s)
11:48:18.774	Interface COM3 closed
11:48:19.195	Interface COM3 open (9600 bit/s)
12:04:02.153	DI
12:04:06.969	EN

The status bar at the bottom indicates: "connected to node 0 at COM3 Enabled DIPROG".

The screenshot shows the FAULHABER Motion Manager software interface. The main editor window displays a test script with the following code:

```

1 |-----|
2 ;Author :
3 ;Date :
4 ;-----|
5 ;Description :
6 |-----|
7 EN
8
9 *LA-2000
10 *M
11 *V100
12 *LR2000
13 *DELAY100
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21

```

The terminal window shows the following communication log:

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12:04:02.153	DI
12:04:06.969	EN

The status bar at the bottom indicates: "connected to node 0 at COM3 Enabled DIPROG".

```
1 ;Author      :   AMEL MEKAOUI
2 ;Description :   MOTION RIGHT AND LEFT IN A LOOP
3
4      EN      ; Switches on the output stage of the control
5      SP10000 ;Load maximum speed. Setting applies to all modes [mm/s].
6      LL-5000 ;Load limit positions lower limit FOR THE POSITION
7      LL5000  ;UPPER limit FOR THE POSITION
8      APL1    ;Activate range limits (LL) (valid for all operating modes except VOLTMOD)
9      HO     ;SETTING THE HOME POSITION
10     AC10000
11     DEC100
12     V5000   ;velocidade
13     V-5000
```

Linear DC-Servomotors

9,2 N

with Analog Hall Sensors

LM 2070 ... 11

Values at 22°C	LM 2070 ... 11		
Continuous force	$F_{e,max.}$	9,2	N
Peak force	$F_{p,max.}$	27,6	N
Continuous current	$I_{e,max.}$	0,79	A
Peak current	$I_{p,max.}$	2,37	A
Back-EMF constant	K_E	9,5	V/m/s
Force constant	K_F	11,64	N/A
Terminal resistance, phase-phase	R	10,83	Ω
Terminal inductance, phase-phase	L	1 125	μH
Thermal resistance	R_{th1} / R_{th2}	3,1 / 9,3	K/W
Thermal time constant	τ_{w1} / τ_{w2}	30 / 1 200	s
Operating temperature range		-20 ... +125	°C
Magnetic pitch	τ_m	24	mm
Rod bearings		polymer sleeves	
Housing material		metal, non-magnetic	
Direction of movement		electronically reversible	

	LM 2070-	040-11	080-11	120-11	160-11	220-11	
Stroke length	$S_{max.}$	40	80	120	160	220	mm
Repeatability	σ_r	60	60	60	60	80	μm
Accuracy	σ_a	200	300	400	500	600	μm
Acceleration	$a_{e,max.}$	93,9	65,7	54,8	46	36,8	m/s^2
Speed	$v_e,max.$	1,9	2,3	2,6	2,7	2,8	m/s
Rod length	L_1	134	182	218	254	314	mm
Rod mass	m_m	98	140	168	200	250	g
Total mass	m_t	236	278	306	338	388	g

Note: These motors are for operation with DC-voltage < 75 V DC. The given values are for free standing motors. Other rod lengths available on request.

Motor characteristic curves

Trapezoidal motion profile ($t_1 = t_2 = t_3$)

Displacement distance: 40 mm
 Friction coefficient: 0,2
 Slope angle: 0°
 Rest time: 0,1 s

Load:

The max. applicable load (incl. rod) at a given speed with an external force of 0 N

External force:

The max. permissible external force at a given speed with a load (incl. rod) of:

- 0,5 kg ———
- 1,0 kg - - - - -
- 2,0 kg ⋯⋯⋯

For notes on technical data and lifetime performance refer to "Technical Information".
 Edition 2019

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Dimensional drawing

Option, cable and connection information

Example product designation: **LM2070-040-11**

Option	Type	Description	Connection				
			-11/-11C		-01		
			No.	Function	No.	Function	Color
-11C	Connector 	Material PVC, 10 conductors, AWG 28 with connector A05a - TCO, pitch 2 mm	1	Phase C	1	Phase C	yellow
			2	Phase B	2	Hall sensor A	green
			3	Phase A	3	U _{DD} (+5V)	red
			4	GND	4	GND	black
			5	U _{DD} (+5V)	5	Hall sensor B	blue
			6	Hall sensor C	6	Hall sensor C	grey
			7	Hall sensor B	7	Phase B	orange
			8	Hall sensor A	8	Phase A	brown
			9	N.C.	9	N.C.	white
			10	N.C.	10	N.C.	purple
			Standard cable				
			Material PVC, 10 conductors, AWG 28, grid 1mm, wires tinned.				

Option, cable and connection information

Example product designation: **LM2070-040-11**

Option	Type	Description	Connection																																																								
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-01	Single wires	Material PVC, 10 conductors, AWG 28. Recommended connector: Molex - Nr. 51110-1060	Standard cable Material PVC, 10 conductors, AWG 28, grid 1mm, wires tinned.																																																								

Product combination

Drive Electronics	Cables / Accessories		
MCLM 3003 P MCLM 3006 S MC 5004 P MC 5004 P STO MC 5005 S	To view our large range of accessory parts, please refer to the "Accessories" chapter.		

For notes on technical data and lifetime performance refer to "Technical Information".
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SUMMARY

THE ROBOTIC THERAPY: THE ASSESSMENT OF AN ACTIVE ORTHOSIS FOR THE REHABILITATION OF FLEXION AND EXTENSION OF THE WRIST FOR PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS LA THÉRAPIE ROBOTIQUE:

Parkinson's disease is the second most common degenerative disease in the world. With more than 6 million cases worldwide, it becomes a public health problem after 60 years old and brings many scientific research projects. The main symptoms being physical symptoms such as tremor, bradykinesia and muscle rigidity, we easily understand that the quality of life of these patients becomes largely limited.

Muscular rigidity impacts freedom of movement and relatively decreases members' ability to move.

For this project, we focused in the movement of the wrist and we retained the movement of flexion and extension.

This report describes my missions during my internship period. I describe my role in the development of computer programming of the prosthesis and the restoration of the prototype.

I also describe my work in the life of the NIATS laboratory.

Using the Faulhaber Motion Manager software, I developed two scripts that allowed me to activate the prosthesis. The first one can be used to control wrist tremors and the second to help the patient flex and extend his wrist.

Key-words: Parkinson's disease, Prosthesis, Rehabilitation, Active orthosis, Robotic therapy

RESUME

ÉVALUATION D'UNE ORTHÈSE ACTIVE POUR LA RÉADAPTATION DU POIGNET DANS SA FLEXION ET SON EXTENSION POUR LES PATIENTS ATTEINTS DE LA MALADIE DE PARKINSON

La maladie de parkinson est la deuxième maladie dégénérative dans le monde. Avec plus de 6 millions de cas à travers la planète, elle devient un problème de santé publique après 60 ans et regroupe de nombreux projet de recherches scientifique. Les symptômes principaux étant des symptômes physiques tels que des tremblements, la bradykinésie et la rigidité musculaire, nous comprenons facilement que la qualité de vie de ces patients devient largement limitée. La rigidité musculaire impacte la liberté de mouvement et diminue de manière relative les capacités de motion des membres.

Pour ce projet, nous nous sommes intéressé au mouvement du poignet et nous retenons le mouvement de flexion et d'extension de celui-ci.

Ce rapport décrit mes missions durant ma période de stage. Je décris mon rôle dans le développement de la programmation informatique de la prothèse ainsi que mes autres missions concernant la réparation du prototype déjà réalisé avant mon arrivé.

Je décris également mon travail effectué dans la vie du laboratoire NIATS ainsi que mes expériences lors des congrès nationaux qui ont eu lieu au Brésil pendant cette période de travail.

A l'aide du logiciel Faulhaber Motion Manager, j'ai pu développer deux scripts me permettant d'activer la prothèse. Le premier pouvant être utiliser dans le but de contrôler les tremblements du poignet et le deuxième servant à aider le patient a effectuer un mouvement de flexion et d'extension de son poignet.

Mots clés : Maladie de Parkinson, Prothèse, Réhabilitation, Orthèse active, Thérapie robotique